

1 **Brachyury (T) is modulated during lung cancer progression.**

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7 Depletion of p53 by shRNA in bronchial epithelial cells of the lung resulted in repression of T
8 demonstrating tumor suppressor control of fate choice through the germ layer commitment program. In
9 humans with small-cell lung cancer, T (brachyury) was activated in lymph node metastasis. The data
10 demonstrate specific, patterned changes in a Tbx homeobox during cancer progression in a T-box gene
11 controlled by a tumor suppressor and a specific marker of germ layer commitment.

12 Citations

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14 1. Shah SR, David JM, Tippens ND, et al. Brachyury-YAP Regulatory Axis Drives Stemness and
15 Growth in Cancer. Cell Rep. 2017;21(2):495-507. doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2017.09.057
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